

СЕКЦИОННЫЕ ДОКЛАДЫ

СЕКЦИЯ 1. ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ТЕОРИЯ

Гаджиев А.Г.

Азербайджан, Баку, Институт экономики НАНА

MODEL OF MAKROECONOMIC REGULATION IN AZERBAIJAN IN CONDITIONS OF HIGH INFLATION

The report discusses the model of macroeconomic regulation in Azerbaijan in the conditions of a high level of "imported" inflation. A new solution is proposed for the central bank's main task of analyzing and evaluating a "favorable" level of inflation for the economy. Thus, two periods are established for the medium term: (a) effective periods for stimulating inflation growth in terms of activating private investment in the non-oil sector of the economy; (b) periods in which the need is to ensure price stability. In other words, periods are determined, in which it is necessary to expand the money supply in circulation in order to increase the stimulation of production growth and periods of reduction in the growth rate of the money supply in order to ensure price stability.

Over the past twenty years, the achievement of a minimum level of inflation has consistently been a priority of Azerbaijan's monetary policy (with the exception of the periods of the financial crisis of 2015-2016 and 2020, when financial stability was a priority). The main directions of regulation, as is known, are instruments of direct regulation of the monetary base (respectively, the money supply in circulation), monetary policy instruments – parameters of the exchange rate regime of the national currency, currency regime, as well as, to a certain extent, changes in the parameters of the discount rate, the boundaries of the interest rate corridor, etc.

Along with the parameters of monetary policy, in order to achieve the established priority, the parameters of fiscal policy are also adjusted – changes are made in the tax system and in the implemented tax policy (adjustment of the level of indirect taxes – VAT and excises, parameters of taxation of personal income, taxes applied at public and private sector enterprises, etc.). In addition, the level of transfers from SOFAZ (State Oil Fund of the Azerbaijan Republic) to the state budget of the country is annually considered and approved by the Parliament of the country, taking into account the requirements for ensuring the established priority.

As the experience of past years shows, this approach as a whole provides only necessary, but not sufficient, conditions for achieving stable economic

growth in the country. Within the framework of existing principles, it is very often not possible to ensure positive dynamics in real values of a number of parameters (in the dynamics of real values of the interest rate, the national currency exchange rate, growth in household incomes, etc.) that have a decisive influence on the nature and quality of economic growth. This situation causes problems in achieving a stable growth in economic activity, including in the dynamics of the growth of private investment in the non-oil sector of the economy and, accordingly, in ensuring employment growth. In this regard, recessions and stagnations periodically observed in the economy clearly indicate the need to adjust the current system of macroeconomic regulation, both in terms of improving the tools used and in the mechanisms for their coordination.

In principle, achieving price stability as a macroeconomic policy priority is a generally accepted approach, both in theory and in practice of macroeconomic regulation. In other words, this approach underlies many theoretical studies and functioning models of macroeconomic regulation in many countries. Since it is believed that ensuring a low level of inflation with a positive dynamics of the parameters of the balance of payments is a sufficient condition for ensuring the sustainability of economic growth. And if there is a high level of inflation in the economy and there are problems in the parameters of the balance of payments (uncontrolled growth of the deficit in current operations or in the movement of capital), then this is due to the inefficiency of the current system of macroeconomic regulation and, in particular, in the coordination of fiscal and monetary policy instruments.

Illustration1. Share of budget expenditures in GDP (in %)

In the practice of macroeconomic regulation in Azerbaijan over the past two decades, there were indeed periods in which it was necessary to reduce the high rates of price growth observed in the economy and the establishment of a low level of inflation as a priority in regulation was a necessity. However, along with this, there were periods in the economy in which the reduction of the inflation

rate from the average values acceptable in terms of ensuring economic growth to the minimum was not an effective regulation regime. Since, in the short term, such regulation determined the negative impact on the increase in employment in the economy, and in the long term on economic development as a whole.

For this reason, the generally accepted practice of setting annual inflation at the level of 2-3% as a priority, if effective for developed countries, this practice may not always be effective for developing economies, including Azerbaijan. The research results [1, 2] show that the dynamics and real values of the parameters that determine the growth of the economy can be favorable in conditions of high inflation (and vice versa).

In other words, if inflation does not exceed a certain upper limit, and if it does not cause a negative impact on the real values of the regulated basic parameters, then measures to further reduce it are ineffective, and the costs incurred are lost to the economy. Only in those cases when the current level of inflation has a negative impact on the real values of the parameters, its level is considered high and the priority of macroeconomic regulation is to reduce it.

Analyzing the dynamics of inflation, economic growth and the main parameters of regulation in real terms, the following periods can be distinguished:

- a period of sharp decline in inflation followed by deflation and accelerated economic growth (1995-1999);
- a period of stable low inflation (average annual level of 2-3%) and high economic growth rates (2000-2004);
- a period of high double-digit inflation and high double-digit economic growth (2005-2008);
- a period of low inflation and a rapid decline in economic growth rates and, as a result, the onset of stagnation (2009-2011);
- a period of low inflation and low economic growth rates (2012-2014);
- period of stagflation – high inflation and economic recession, (2015-2017);
- years of low inflation and low economic growth (2018-2019);
- period of low inflation and economic recession (2020);
- years of accelerated inflation and economic growth (2021-2022).

In the Statements of the Central Bank of Azerbaijan [3] the need to form mechanisms to achieve effective coordination between inflation and economic growth levels is noted as an urgent problem.

It is known that not an abundance of theoretical studies on establishing a direct relationship between inflation and economic growth did not give concrete and acceptable results. Recently, as a basis for the analysis of links, it is proposed to use changes determined by inflation in other economic parameters, which in turn affect economic growth. One of the most common studies in this area is the use of the existing correlation between inflation and real money supply (adjusted for inflation at the level of the monetary aggregate M2), and then real money

supply (RMS) and economic growth. That is, the GDP in the economy increases in the following cases: (a) the M2 money supply increases in conditions of price stability (with a low level of inflation); and b) when the growth rate of the money supply exceeds the rate of inflation. In other words, the acceleration of economic growth is possible even in conditions of high inflation in the country's economy; an important condition for this is the excess of the growth rate of the money supply in circulation over the inflation rate. Accordingly, GDP decreases: (a) when the rate of inflation in the economy exceeds the growth rate of the nominal money supply; and (b) when the contraction of the money supply occurs with price stability. In other words, if there is (observed) a specific relationship between RMS and GDP, then it is possible to establish the relationship between the inflation rate and the economic growth rate.

In world practice, there are enough examples confirming this dependence, and a good example is the macroeconomic regulation regime applied in Turkey. Thus, in recent years, the Turkish economy has seen a substantial depreciation of the Turkish lira, an acceleration of inflation while reducing the interest rate by the central bank, which resulted in an increase in the level of GDP, aggregate demand, the level of the country's gold and foreign exchange reserves, etc. in the economy.

Table 1

Inflation, economic growth and monetary regulation parameters

Periods	Years	Inflation	Economic growth	M2 (index of growth)	Real money supply	Real exchange rate
1.	1996	19,9	101,3	2,22	1,85	75
	1997	3,7	105,8	1,26	1,21	90
	1998	-0,8	110	1,29	1,30	105
	1999	-8,5	107,4	0,78	0,86	110
2.	2000	1,8	111,1	1,15	1,13	100
	2001	1,5	109,9	1,16	1,14	96,4
	2002	2,8	110,6	1,08	1,05	87,1
	2003	2,2	111,2	1,48	1,44	75,4
	2004	6,7	110,2	1,25	1,17	73,8
3.	2005	9,6	126,4	1,16	1,06	81,4
	2006	8,3	134,5	1,04	0,96	84,5
	2007	16,7	125	1,07	0,92	89,1
	2008	20,8	110,8	1,38	1,14	114,1
4.	2009	1,5	109,3	1,01	1,00	110
	2010	4,1	105	1,34	1,29	115,3
	2011	7,9	100,1	1,33	1,23	121,6
5.	2012	1,1	102,2	1,26	1,24	114,8
	2013	2,4	105,8	1,19	1,16	120,3
	2014	1,4	102,8	1,06	1,05	140,7

End of Table 1

6.	2015	3,7	103,1	0,50	0,48	107,6
	2016	12,4	96,9	1,33	1,18	86,3
	2017	12,9	100,2	1,08	0,96	89,8
7.	2018	2,3	101,5	1,17	1,15	95,4
	2019	2,6	102,5	1,25	1,21	93,4
8.	2020	2,8	95,8	1,11	1,08	97,1
9.	2021	6,7	105,6	1,18	1,10	109,2
	2022	13,9	104,6	1,24	0,9	122,3

As mentioned above, the report discusses an alternative mechanism for the current macroeconomic regulation regime applied in Azerbaijan, that is, the possibility of creating macroeconomic conditions that can stimulate the development of the non-oil sector of the economy in conditions of high inflation. Such an approach can ensure the achievement of positive changes in the dynamics of real indicators – the real and effective exchange rate of the national currency, the real interest rate, real incomes of the population, the level and structure of private investment in the non-oil sector, the level and structure of budget revenues, etc.

As part of this approach, the central bank should identify periods of stimulating inflation growth that are effective in terms of activating private investment in the non-oil sector and periods of ensuring price stability, periods of expanding the money supply in order to stimulate growth in production, and periods of reducing the growth rate of the money supply in order to ensure price stability. In other words, within the framework of this regulation, the main component is the correct establishment of these periods; otherwise, the current regulatory system may cause instability in the dynamics of production [4-10].

In the medium term, within the framework of the current model of macroeconomic regulation in Azerbaijan, 3 (three) scenarios for the development of the situation are possible, and all three scenarios are based on the expected changes in the country's balance of payments:

1. baseline scenario (the scenario determined by the Government of the country) – the positive balance of payments remains, but the surplus decreases;
2. pessimistic scenario – a deficit in the balance of payments is formed;
3. optimistic scenario – the positive balance of payments increases.

In all three scenarios, inflation risks, currency risks, interest rate risks, liquidity risks in banks and possible consequences of adjusting key regulatory parameters should be assessed.

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